

E5.1 Design of Operational Components and Toolkit for Automated Discovery and SLA Assurance

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List of Acronyms

6G	Sixth Generation
B5G	Beyond 5G
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OAS	OpenAPI Specification
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
REST	Representational State Transfer
SCSC	Smart Contract State Composer
SL	Supervised Learning
SLA	Service Level Agreement
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to the deliverable *E5.1 Design of Operational Components and Toolkit for Automated Discovery and SLA Assurance*, envisaged in the framework of the project 6GENABLERS-DLT (TSI-063000-2021-12). This deliverable marks the initial progress of Work Package 5 (P5), which centres on the pivotal aspects of SLA Assurance. P5 focuses on developing innovative methods to monitor and anticipate any violation on the SLA terms of active orders within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. The primary objective of P5 is to enrich the 6GENABLERS Marketplace with data analytics tools monitoring metrics established in the SLA, notifying and registering any violation or restoration of the target value. When marketplace orders turn active, the tools capture metrics from network and virtualized assets linked with the terms defined in the SLA clauses of active orders. In order to enable data analytics, the tools aggregate and store metrics as time series to enable real-time processing and forensics. Finally, the tools identify alarms or forecast alerts according to the negotiated conditions of the SLA in the order. Within this context, E5.1 provides an extensive overview of the design framework and specifications for the operational components and toolkit required by the proactive SLA assurance within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. This document elucidates the technical intricacies, architectural considerations, and data models that form the foundation of these critical functionalities. In essence, this deliverable offers a comprehensive blueprint for the implementation of SLA Assurance services within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. It underscores the importance of automation and customization in meeting user requirements effectively, laying the groundwork for these crucial features.

1 Introduction

In the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, Service Level Agreement (SLA) Assurance is a fundamental service, which play crucial roles in ensuring the reliable and auditable operation of the platform as provides a monitoring tool that detects and forecasts any infraction or restoration of the defined metrics when compared with the target values to be notified to the Marketplace systems. Thus, it provides awareness to other components which can potentially trigger an actuation.

SLA Assurance is responsible for monitoring and enforcing the SLA established between parties in the Marketplace. As a first step, this system takes care of launching the deployment of the acquired resources and services. From this point onwards, it performs the tracking of Quality of Service (QoS) measurements relevant for the services and resources being provided and ensuring they meet the agreed-upon standards. These metrics are used to determine the fulfilment of SLAs and provide consumers and providers with insights into the quality of services. In cases where SLAs are not met, SLA Assurance makes sure this incident is correctly stored in the ledger, making it available for consultation and further analytics in the case of disputes. Based on the continuous monitoring and real-time analysis, SLA Assurance can also foresee potential order degradations and proactively alert on upcoming alarms before they are identified.

In this context, the deliverable *E5.1 Design of Operational Components and Toolkit for Automated Discovery and SLA Assurance* provides a comprehensive overview of the design framework and specifications for the operational components and toolkit essential to the automation of resource and service discovery and proactive SLA assurance within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. This document elucidates the technical aspects, architectural considerations, and data models that underpin these critical functionalities.

1.1 Document Scope and Objectives

This deliverable outlines the initial outcomes from Work Package 5 (P5), dedicated to unveiling the promising value of the SLA Assurance, as core services of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace services. As such, this document provides the design of the operational components and toolkit envisioned for SLA Assurance. In particular, each system is detailed in terms of design guidelines, internal architecture, interfaces, data models and workflow examples.

In correspondence with the aforementioned scope, the primary objectives of this document are as follows:

1. **Module Design Description:** The primary objective of this deliverable is to meticulously describe the design of operational modules providing SLA assurance. It provides detailed insights into the structural and functional aspects of these modules, highlighting their roles and interactions within the broader platform.
2. **Service Mapping and Integration:** The document aims to map the provided services within the context of the overall Marketplace platform. It elucidates how these operational components seamlessly integrate with other components, ensuring cohesiveness and synergy.

3. Interface and Data Model Specifications: An essential objective is to provide precise specifications for interfaces and service endpoints associated with these systems. This includes detailing the exposed operations, input and output formats and communication mechanisms to enable seamless interactions.
4. Operational Patterns: The deliverable outlines the sequence diagrams that drive the execution of SLA assurance procedures. It specifies workflow examples for this system facilitating a clear understanding of the underlying operational patterns.

By achieving these objectives, this deliverable provides a robust framework and toolkit for SLA assurance, laying the foundation for service quality within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

1.2 Relation to the Project's Activities

This deliverable presents the initial outcomes from Work Package 5 (P5), which covers the pillars related to SLA Assurance. This work package focuses on investigating and developing novel approaches to perform the monitoring and tracking of SLA terms in the Marketplace orders. The goal of this work package is to enrich the 6GENABLERS Marketplace with analytical tools to apply monitoring, storage and analytical processing of the SLAs status.

As depicted in Figure 1-1, deliverable E5.1 is the result of the work done in the task A5.2 within P5, A5.2 – Proactive SLA Assurance: This task focuses on automating SLA signing underpinned by the Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) capabilities. Moreover, it is meant to keep track of contract conditions and QoS measurements, ensuring violations are recorded on the ledger, as mechanisms for SLA assurance. Finally, this task will be interlinked to A5.1. The SLA Assurance will provide awareness of issues of the SLA status to fire reactions by the Marketplace actors or systems, which could query the smart discovery of Marketplace offers as a means to avoid potential SLA violations.

Figure 1-1 E5.1 positioning and relation to the project's activities

The work captured in this deliverable takes as input the system requirements defined within P2 [1], and in particular by A2.5 (SLA Assurance System Requirements). At the same time, the modular design of the different components to be developed within P5 and provided in this document will feed the definition of the overall 6GENABLERS Marketplace architecture as part of A2.6 (DLT-anchored Smart Marketplace Architecture). Furthermore, this design will guide the subsequent development of prototypes to be carried out in P5, while ensuring the required interactions with other components associated to P3 and P4.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The current document is structured in several sections that detail the design specifications of the platform components defined to meet the goal of SLA assurance. In particular, the document is structured as follows:

- Section 1: This section provides an overview of the document, including its objectives, the relationship to the project's activities, and the structure of the document itself.
- Section 2: This section presents the detailed specifications of the SLA assurance system, providing the internal components architecture, interfaces, data models and workflow examples.
- Section 3: The conclusion section summarises the main findings and highlights the key takeaways from the document.
- Section 4: This section lists the sources and references cited throughout the document, providing a comprehensive list of the materials used to support the information presented.

2 SLA Assurance System Specification

Within this section, we introduce the preliminary specifications of the components responsible for delivering SLA Assurance capabilities. Our aim is to provide a comprehensive depiction of the system, serving as a foundation for precise implementation tasks within P5. It's essential to acknowledge that these component specifications may undergo refinements and adjustments during the implementation phase, which will be duly reflected in upcoming deliverables E5.2 and E5.3. Furthermore, this effort directly contributes to shaping the overarching architecture, initially outlined in E2.2 and subsequently refined in E2.3.

2.1 Overview

The introduction of the SLA Assurance application is of paramount importance on the 6GENABLERS platform. This block introduces the intelligence in order to ensure that the SLA is not violated using real-time monitoring techniques in order to have knowledge about the network status.

2.2 Design Guidelines

The SLA Assurance includes several components that create a closed-loop to continuously monitor and control infrastructures according to the orders signed in a 6GENABLERS Marketplace. This means that the loop listens for orders and triggers processes which apply configurations and monitor the included network assets reporting any infraction. Beyond this monitor and control loop, the components need to provide information to other systems in the Marketplace. To this end, the information is published in a messaging platform to allow other systems to get awareness on the provided network status and any issue raised. To ensure the efficient execution, the SLA Assurance runs individual loops per incoming order request, avoiding the processing of metrics when they are not part of an order to track. Accordingly, the loop is terminated as the order is retired. The data analytics loop is compatible with different runtime modes, being able to work on push or pull mode to trigger metrics processing. To accommodate all these features in the SLA Assurance development a set of comprehensive design guidelines has been formulated.

These guidelines are strategically crafted to facilitate the development, deployment, pipelining of components and utilisation of the information produced in a manner that aligns with both technical excellence and versatile functionality. So, the practices that underpin the successful implementation of the SLA assurance components are listed below:

- **Modular Architecture:** Develop the SLA assurance components as a modular architecture to ensure scalability, maintainability, interoperability. This facilitates the addition of new functionalities or updates without disrupting the entire system.
- **Separation of Concerns:** Divide the components into well-defined functional entities, each responsible for a specific task (such as order listener and parser, brokerage of orchestrators, metrics capture, metrics aggregation and persistence, metrics evaluation, issue notification and messaging). This

enhances clarity, ease of troubleshooting, independent development and extensible features.

- **Message-driven Protocol:** Implement a message-driven protocol that allows seamless interaction across SLA Assurance components and other modules of the Marketplace framework. Clearly define the input and output formats for each event, information and notification to ensure smooth integration. Being able to update status of asynchronous tasks such as the brokered resource controls.
- **Effective Processing:** Implement listeners to execute processors when messages are received. The message would trigger network provisioning, monitoring and reporting.
- **Real-time Processing:** Implement mechanisms for real-time processing of incoming order requests. Consider the clauses in the order, the network assets included to allocate, configure and run, the metrics to monitor and the messages to share information about the network status or the conditions satisfaction.
- **Configurability:** Provide configuration options for setting parameters like forecasting algorithms, evaluation period, monitoring intervals, sampling rate, among others. This allows system administrators to customize the component to suit specific needs.
- **Automated deployment:** Providing scripts to automate deployment of components, configuration of connectivity, and loading of settings including the indexing of local systems to apply orders, including local allocation, instantiation, configuration and free, and probe monitoring systems to data analytics tools for SLA breach detection and forecast.

By adhering to these guidelines, the SLA assurance components can embody a robust architecture, scalable capabilities, and advanced functionalities, providing a loop for monitoring and controlling active orders in real time, registering and notifying any issue. Following these design guidelines ensures that the SLA assurance component is not only technically robust but also flexible enough to process different orders and satisfy the system's objectives.

2.3 Sub-components

The SLA Assurance system serves the primary purpose of ensuring that there is no violation of the SLA established in the deployed order, it means, that the offer conditions once ordered and instantiated meet the SLA requirements. Specifically, this module monitors the network in real-time and facilitates knowing about the Smart Contract status.

The internal architecture of the SLA Assurance system depicted in Figure 2-1 comprises five subcomponents following the design guideline of modularity. These subcomponents are collectively supported by a set of monitoring, messaging, and orchestration tools. It also uses time series databases to store metrics collected during monitoring.

Figure 2-1 SLA Assurance internal architecture

The SLA Assurance is composed by the following sub-components: Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator, Data Lake, Proactive SLA Monitoring, Data Bus and Broker Logic for Resource Controller as shown in Figure 2-1, and their functionality is described below.

- **Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator:** The Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator is responsible for monitoring the network metrics at a different level of the network collected from different infrastructure segments as well as, read from Data Bus the SLA rules. During runtime, this entity pushes all the collected metrics into the “Data Lake” component.
- **Data Lake:** Data Lake is an entity responsible for the registration and storage of all the metrics collected in a time series database (Prometheus, Thanos, etc.). It allows to Proactive SLA Monitoring to read all the metrics monitored by the “Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator” component, for their analysis.
- **Proactive SLA Monitoring:** The Proactive SLA Monitoring block is responsible for checking the recollected network infrastructure metrics with the values imposed by the Smart Contract, in order to determine if there is an SLA violation. The Network infrastructure metrics are read from the Data Lake, and the SLA imposed metric is read from the Data Bus. Moreover, it is responsible for predicting the SLA next value metric in order to alert the system whether an SLA violation is going to happen or not. In case of an SLA status changed, or the prediction of the SLA metric value, this component sends all the data to the Data

Bus. Then, the Smart Contract State Composer will read from the Data Bus if an SLA breach has been occurred. .

- **Data Bus:** The Data Bus provides real-time communication between components in the system such as the services in the Zero Touch Platform, the Data Analytics components, and the Marketplace APIs. Using Kafka as the event streaming platform for the Data Bus will provide the capability for services to read to and write from specific topics.
- **Broker Logic for Resource Controller:** Broker Logic for Resource Controller is the responsible module for the handling of actions requested to deploy resources in the Network Infrastructure related to the requirements from Smart Contracts. This module will be listening on the Data Bus to capture requests to deploy resources. Once a request has been launched, the Broker will communicate with Network Controllers to check if the resource is available, and it will deploy and configure it in an affirmative case announcing that the deployment is ongoing in the Data Bus. If resources are not available, it will announce the lack of availability to the Data Bus. Broker logic for resource controller has three main blocks depicted in Figure 2-2:
 - Action manager
 - Action Engine
 - Catalogue manager

Figure 2-2 Architecture for Broker Logic for Resource Controller

Action manager is responsible for monitoring Data Bus to get messages from Ordering API [3] for deploying and configuring resources in the Network Infrastructure. Action manager is responsible too for announcing into the Data Bus the state of the deployment

launched in the Network Infrastructure service with status messages like the ones shown in Table 2-1:

Table 2-1 Broker for resource logic order deployment status

Status	Description
Resource deploying	Resource is being deployed
Resource ready	Resource has been deployed
Error	There was an error in the deployment

Action Engine will be the responsible for mapping requests coming from Action Manager to the appropriate Network Infrastructure to be configured.

Catalogue manager is responsible for checking catalogue of resources from Asset providers and ensuring that resources requested from Action Manager are available and up and running.

Broker Logic for Resource Controller can control several technologies such as:

- i2Slicer [2]
 - Slice Manager
 - RAN Controller
- External API
 - OpenStack [4]
 - OSM [5]
 - Amarisoft [6]
 - Kubernetes [7] through Helm chart [8] deployment

2.4 Interfaces and Data Models

In terms of interfaces, SLA Assurance is expected to interact with the rest of the Marketplace through Data Bus. Figure 2-3, shows the interfaces and the communication between the SLA Assurance with the other external components.

Figure 2-3 Interfaces of SLA Assurance with other components

Data Bus will be the central communication node for almost all elements of SLA Assurance, providing the communication and interaction resources for almost all elements. The only exception to this, will be the communication between Data Lake and Monitor & Network Analytics Aggregator that will communicate each other through an API.

2.4.1 Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator

The Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator will have connection with the Network Infrastructure and with the Data Bus. On the one hand, this block will listen from the Data Bus for the status of the deployment, and, on the other hand, once the deployment of the Network Infrastructure is in “Resource Ready” state, it will collect all the network metrics provided by the Network Infrastructure. The messages read from the Data Bus in order to have all the information, are the ones that are described in Table 2-2.

Table 2-2 Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator

Field	Type	Description	Example
Order_DID	String	Identifier	{"order_DID": "550e8400-e29b-41d4-a716"}
createdAt	DateTime	Date and time at which the event took place	{"timestamp": "2019-10-11T09:21:04.981Z"}
SLA	JSON	All the information about the deployment status, the SLA rules, and the network infrastructure metrics url for getting metrics	<pre> {"orderId": "string", "ordererStatus": "status_of_the_deployment", "SLA": [[9]], "metricAddress": "url"} </pre> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [9] List of SLA rules

2.4.2 Data Lake

The Data Lake component will have connection with the Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator component, which inserts the network infrastructure metrics into the Data Lake. The delivery of the metrics is performed by the Prometheus Pushgateway, in order to push there all the metrics. The, the Prometheus will read all the metrics pushed in the Pushgateway. On the other hand, it will have connection with the Proactive SLA Monitoring, which reads network infrastructure metrics from the Data Lake.

2.4.3 Proactive SLA Monitoring

The Proactive SLA Monitoring will have the following connection points:

- Data Bus
- Data Lake

Proactive SLA Monitoring will read the network metrics from the Data Lake and will check with the SLA rules, which are read from the Data Bus.

Is important to differentiate between an SLA violation and the prediction of the SLA violation. If exists any SLA violation, that is, a violation has occurred, this block will send the violated metric and an alarm to the Data Bus as it is shown in Table 2-3. The SCSC is responsible for reading the Data Bus and send that data to the SC-State API actions.

Table 2-3 Proactive SLA Monitoring alarm event

Field	Type	Description	Example
SLA_DID	String	Identifier	{"SLA_DID": "550e8400-e29b-41d4-a716"}
createdAt	DateTime	Date and time at which the event took place	{"timestamp": "2019-10-11T09:21:04.981Z"}
SLA	JSON Array	SLA rules and metrics for reading and checking with the measured of the network infrastructure	{ "SLA": [[9]], "alarm": true/false } [9] List of SLA rules

If the prediction of SLA detects that the SLA violation is near of violation, this block will send an alert to the Data Bus, as it is described in Table 2-4.

Table 2-4 Proactive SLA Monitoring alert event

Field	Type	Description	Example
SLA_DID	String	Identifier	{"SLAID": "550e8400-e29b-41d4-a716"}
createdAt	DateTime	Date and time at which the event took place	{"timestamp": "2019-10-11T09:21:04.981Z"}
SLA	JSON Array	SLA rules and metrics for reading and checking with	{ "SLA": [[9]], "alert": true/false }

		the measured of the network infrastructure	[[9]] List of SLA rules
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2.4.4 Data Bus

The Data Bus will have connection points with the components in the Zero Touch Platform, the DLT APIs, Data Analytics and with the Smart Contract State Composer.

The full list of topics defined in the Data Bus is defined in Table 2-5 below:

Table 2-5 Topic Definitions

Topic Name	Producer	Consumer	Purpose of message being sent	Message Format
alert	Proactive SLA Monitoring	SCSC	Alert the system of a potential breach of the SLA rules so that it can be resolved	Table 2-4
alarm	Proactive SLA Monitoring	SCSC	Record a change of status of the SLA rules compliance to be persisted	Table 2-3
deployment_status	Broker Logic for Resource Controller	SCSC & Monitoring and Network Analytics Aggregator	Indicate the status of resource deployment	Table 2-8
deployment_request	SC-State API	Broker Logic for Resource Controller	Trigger the deployment of resources	Table 2-6
availability_request	Offering API	Broker Logic for Resource Controller	Indicate a new Offer of resources that needs to have its availability monitored	Table 2-7
availability_response	Broker Logic for Resource Controller	SCSC	Indicate the availability of an offered resource	Table 2-8

The Data Bus will receive data from the DLT APIs to notify subscribers of incoming requests. When a new Smart Contract State is created, the SC-State API will write a message to the Data Bus. This message (defined in Table 2-6) is read by the Broker Logic for Resource Controller to trigger the deployment of resources.

Table 2-6 Message to be sent from SC-State API to Data Bus

Field	Type	Description	Example value
orderID	string	Identifier of the created order	"ord1234ertet4wert"

type	string	Type of resource to be deployed	"CPU"
SLA	JSON Array	A list of metrics that will be fulfilled.	[<pre>{ "metric": "down-time ", "limitValue": "120", "metricOperator": "<" }</pre>]
resources	Object	Specifications of resources	"resources":{ <pre>"flavour": "string_low_mid_high", "memory": "int", "cpu": "int", "disk": "int", "freq": "int", "bandwidth": "int", "helm": "string_url" }</pre>

The Offering API also writes to the Data Bus once a new offer is added to the system. This message is read by the Broker Logic for Resource Controller which then checks the availability of the offered resource. This message is described in Table 2-7.

Table 2-7 Message to be sent from the Offering API to the Data Bus

Field	Type	Description	Example value
offerId	string	Identifier of the created offer	"off1234ertet4wert"
type	string	Type of resource to be offered	"CPU"
productSpecification	Object	The specification of the resource that is being offered	{ <pre>"product spec": "string", "flavour": "string_low_mid_high", "memory": "int", "cpu": "int", "disk": "int", "freq": "int", "bandwidth": "int", "helm": "string" }</pre>
validFor	Object	Specifications of the resource to be deployed	{ <pre>"startDateTime": "string", "endDateTime": "string" }</pre>

Once a resource is deployed, the Broker Logic for Resource Controller writes a confirmation message to the Data Bus which is subsequently read by the Monitoring and Network Analytics Aggregator to start the monitoring.

Figure 2-4 shows an example of how the Data Bus connects to the other components in the system.

Figure 2-4 Communication between components via the Data Bus

2.4.5 Broker Logic for Resource Controller

Broker Logic for Resource Controller will listen Data Bus for incoming requests from SC STATE API and will act in a synchronous way when a new Request is received. Broker Logic for Resource Controller will send events to the Data Bus based on the situations given by dataflows in Section 2.5.5.

Table 2-8 Broker Logic for Resource Controller events

Field	Type	Description
ID	String	Identifier
eventType	String	Resource Availability /Deployment status
createdAt	DateTime	Date and time in which the event took place.
payload	Json	<pre>{resource:"Identifier", available:"yes"}</pre> <pre>{ orderId:"id", orderStatus:"deploying", "SLA":[[9]], "metricAddress": "url" }</pre> [9]List of SLA rules

2.5 Workflow Examples

In this section the workflows and the sequence diagram of each subcomponent of the SLA Assurance is detailed.

2.5.1 Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator

The Figure 2-5 below, describes the workflow in relation to the Monitoring and Network Analytics Aggregator. First, this block gets the status of the deployment and the metrics to be analysed for the SLA, including the metric name, the metric value limit, and the logic operator from the Data Bus. Secondly, this block is responsible for collecting the metrics of the Network Infrastructure once the resources is correctly deployed. It will read from the Data Bus the status of the deployment and depending on the deployment status, it takes different actions.

- **Resource deploying:** This status means that the network infrastructure is not deployed yet, so the monitoring of the network should wait until the infrastructure is already deployed.
- **Error:** This status means that the deployment of the Network Infrastructure has failed, and this module should wait until the error of the deployment is fixed in order to have the infrastructure correctly deployed to start monitoring the network.
- **Resource ready:** This status says that the service requested from the order is already deployed and is working correctly, so the monitoring of the Network Infrastructure can be started. To do so, the Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator requests network metrics in a loop from the Network Infrastructure. To finish this process, all the recollected metrics are sent to a Time Series Database to have a Data Lake with all the recollected metrics.

Figure 2-5 Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator Workflow

2.5.2 Data Lake

The Figure 2-6 shows the workflow related to the Data Lake. When the Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator collects metrics from the network infrastructure once the monitoring of the network has been started, it inserts all the metrics into the Data Lake.

Figure 2-6 Data Lake Workflow

2.5.3 Proactive SLA Monitoring

The Figure 2-7 shows the workflow in relation to the Proactive SLA Monitoring and the communication between components.

First of all, the Proactive SLA monitoring reads from Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator the SLA rules to be analysed, which the SLA rules have been read previously from the Data Bus by the Monitoring & Network Analytics Aggregator. On the other hand, this block reads from the Data Lake in order to obtain the network infrastructure collected metrics.

Once the Proactive SLA has both SLA rules and the Network Infrastructure metric, it checks if there is an SLA status change. Those status change can be:

- From not violated status to SLA violated status
- From SLA violated status to not violated status

When the Proactive SLA monitoring detects an SLA status change an alarm message is sent to the Data Bus. If the status change goes from not violated to violated status, it will send an alarm indicating that a violation has occurred, and the metric value. However, if the status change goes from SLA violation to not SLA violation, it will send a message indicating that all the SLA is correct. The SCSC will read from the Data Bus in order to update the status of the SLA in the DLT in case of an SLA breach.

In parallel, this component will predict SLA metric values in order to anticipate to an SLA violation. In this case, this block will send an alert to the Data Bus indicating that an SLA violation is near to occur.

Figure 2-7 Proactive SLA Monitoring Workflow

2.5.4 Data Bus

Figure 2-8 shows an example of how the specific components within each block use the Data Bus to communicate when a change in SLA Compliance is recorded. The Proactive SLA Monitoring component detects the change and writes it to a topic in the Data Bus. In the case of an SLA compliance alarm, the Smart Contract State Composer (SCSC) reads this message from the Data Bus. The SCSC then uses the SC-State API to store this violation in the Trading DLT. Similarly, in the case of an SLA compliance alert, the SCSC reads this breach from the Data Bus although this does not get stored in the Trading DLT.

Data Bus Workflow Example: SLA Violations

Figure 2-8 Data Bus Workflow during change in SLA compliance status

2.5.5 Broker Logic for Resource Controller

In Figure 2-9, the behaviour of the Broker Logic for Resource Controller when a new offer arrives at the Data Bus is shown:

- Broker monitors Data Bus for New Offer message
- Broker asks to the Network Infrastructure for the availability of resources needed by the Offer.
- If resource is available, Broker pushes to the Data Bus the availability of the resource.
- If resource is not available, Broker pushes that resource is not available to the Data Bus.

Broker Logic for Resource Controller Offer behavior

Figure 2-9 Broker Logic for Resource Controller dataflow when Offer is saved

In Figure 2-10, the dataflow diagram of the Broker Logic for Resource Controller when a new order arrives can be seen. The working flow diagram is the following:

- Smart Contract State Composer launches a deploy resource request to the SC-State API.
- SC-State API forwards that request to the Data Bus.
- Broker monitors Data Bus to get requests.
- Broker connects to Network Infrastructure endpoint to check resource's availability.
- If resource is available, Broker performs a deploy and configure request to the Network Infrastructure passing parameters acquired from Smart Contract deployment request.
- Network Infrastructure answers with a "Resource deploying" message when starting the deployment.
- Broker forwards "Resource deploying" message to the Data Bus adding Smart Contract identifier.
- Smart Contract State Composer monitors Data Bus to get "Resource deploying" message from its previous request.
- Broker polls Network Infrastructure to know when resource has been deployed.

- Broker forwards “Resource ready” message to Data Bus with appropriate Smart Contract identifier.
- Smart Contract State Composer monitors Data Bus to get “Resource ready” message.
- Smart Contract State Composer commands SC-State API to save Order deployment status into the DLT.

Broker Logic for Resource Controller Order behavior

Figure 2-10 Broker Logic for Resource Controller dataflow when Order is required

In Figure 2-11, we can see a dataflow for the internal workflow of the Broker Logic for Resource Controller when an order is requested. The working flow diagram is the following:

- Action Manager monitors Data Bus listening for Deploy and configure action request from SC-State API.
- Action Manager forwards request to Action Engine
- Action Engine maps appropriate destination to the request

- Catalogue manager checks resource availability.
- If resource is available, it forwards that message to Action Engine.
- Action Engine forwards deploy and configure request to Network Infrastructure to start resource deployment.
- Network Infrastructure answers with “Resource deploying”.
- Resource deploying message is forwarded from Action Engine to Action Manager.
- Action Manager polls Network Infrastructure asking for resource deployment status.
- When Resource deployed message is received by Action Engine it will forward it to Action Manager.
- Action Manager will forward “Resource ready” message to Data Bus including Smart Contract identifier.

Broker Logic for Resource Controller Internals

Figure 2-11 Broker Logic for Resource Controller, internal dataflow diagram

3 Conclusion

The document outlines the design framework and specifications for operational components and a toolkit that are crucial for ensuring proactive SLA assurance within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. It delves into technical aspects, architectural considerations, data models, and workflow examples, presenting a comprehensive view of these essential functionalities.

The document underscores the design principles of customization and flexibility, catering to the diverse needs of marketplace stakeholders. It explores how the toolkit and operational components can be adapted to accommodate various scenarios. This ensures that the deliverable addresses the specified acceptance criteria and contributes to the overarching objectives of the project.

In terms of the operation of the SLA Assurance, this document details the components and operational patterns that allow to establish service quality assurance mechanisms by overseeing the SLAs established among Marketplace participants while ensuring violations are properly recorded into the ledger.

The SLA Assurance contributes to the auditable, reliable and data-driven operation of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. The SLA Assurance ensures that these services meet the agreed-upon standards. Together, these components enhance the overall functionality and reliability of the Marketplace, making it a valuable platform for resource and service trading in the 6G ecosystem.

In summary, this deliverable serves as a foundation for SLA Assurance services within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, emphasizing the automation required to meet user needs effectively.

4 References

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